

Current range maps are only shown within the jurisdictional boundaries of the United States of America. The species may also occur outside this region.

• **Wherever found**

Listing status: Endangered

- **States/US Territories** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: Florida, Louisiana, Puerto Rico, Virgin Islands
- **US Counties** in which this population is known to or is believed to occur: [View All](#)
- **USFWS Refuges** in which this population is known to occur:
- **Countries** in which this population is known to occur: Haiti, United States

» **Candidate Information**

No Candidate information available for this species.

No Candidate Assessments available for this species.

Candidate Notice of Review Documents

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title
11/15/1994	59 FR 58982 59028	ETWP; Animal Candidate Review for Listing as Endangered or Threatened Species

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

< Previous 1 Next >

No Uplisting Documents currently available for this species.

» **Federal Register Documents**

Federal Register Documents

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Suppl Doc
12/28/2023	88 FR 89611 89626	Endangered and Threatened Wildlife and Plants; Endangered Species Status for Black-Capped Petrel	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • S A

05/02/2023	88 FR 27427 27430	Threatened Species Status for Black-Capped Petrel With a Section 4(d) Rule
10/09/2018	83 FR 50560 50574	Threatened Species Status for Black-Capped Petrel With a Section 4(d) Rule; Proposed rule.
06/21/2012	77 FR 37367 37373	90-Day Finding on a Petition to List the Black-Capped Petrel as Endangered or Threatened
11/15/1994	59 FR 58982 -----	ETWP; Animal Candidate Review for Listing as Endangered or Threatened Species.

Showing 1 to 5 of 5 entries

» Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

Species Status Assessments (SSAs)

Show entries

Document Date	Document Version	Document Title
05/01/2023	Version 1.3	Species Status Assessment for Black-capped Petrel, v1.3
06/30/2018	Version 1.1	Species Status Assessment Report for Black-capped Petrel (Pterodroma h
04/01/2018	Version 1.0	Species Status Assessment Report for Black-capped Petrel (Pterodroma h

Showing 1 to 3 of 3 entries

Special Rule Publications

No Special Rule Publications currently available for this species.

» Recovery

- [Species with Recovery Documents Data Explorer](#)

No Current Recovery Plans available for this species.

No Other Recovery Documents currently available for this species.

No Five Year Reviews currently available for this species.

No Delisting Documents currently available for this species.

» Critical Habitat

Critical Habitat Documents

Show entries

Date	Citation Page	Title	Critical Habitat Shapefile
------	---------------	-------	----------------------------

10/09/2018	83 FR 50560 50574	Threatened Species Status for Black-Capped Petrel With a Section 4(d) Rule; Proposed rule.
------------	-------------------	--

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

< Previous	1	Next >
------------	---	--------

To learn more about critical habitat please see <https://ecos.fws.gov/crithab>

» Conservation Plans

No Conservation Plans currently available for this species.

» Petitions

Show entries

Petition Title	Date Received by the FWS	Where the species is believed to or known to occur	Petitioner Name	Requested Action	Petition Finding(s)	Active
Petrel, Black-capped (<i>Pterodroma hasitata</i>); List w/ CH	09/06/2011	FL, LA, Puerto Rico, Virgin Islands, Haiti	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wildearth Guardians 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • APA: Petitioned to designate Critical Habitat • ESA - Petitioned for Listing: Threatened or Endangered 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 12m petition finding Warranted on 10/09/2018 • CH Prudency Determination Not prudent at proposed listing on 10/09/2018 • Proposed Threatened on 10/09/2018 • 90 day petition finding Substantial on 06/21/2012 	No - Not Withdra

Showing 1 to 1 of 1 entries

< Previous	1	Next >
------------	---	--------

» Biological Opinions

To see all FWS Issued Biological Opinions please visit the [BO Report](#).

» Life History

Habitat Requirements

The only confirmed active nesting areas at this time are just inland from the southern coast of the island of Hispaniola, a landmass shared by the countries of Haiti (36%) and the Dominican Republic (64%). Confirmed nest sites have been found at elevations from 1700 to 2300 m above sea level (ASL). In most cases, nesting sites are found less than 30 kilometers (km) from the coast. Nesting areas are dominated by *Pinus occidentalis*, sparse understory vegetation, and loose soils or decaying vegetation conducive to burrow excavation. A steep, mountainous terrain composed of dolomitic limestone, or other karst materials, also provides abundant holes, caves, and crevices.

Food Habits

Foraging by Black-capped Petrels occurs mainly (96%) in flocks, with 88% of observed feeding flocks comprised also of other avian species. Such flocks may contain up to 65 Black-capped Petrels. Schools or congregations of baitfish or marine invertebrates have reportedly attracted petrels in feeding assemblages of up to 12 other seabird species, with individual feeding bouts typically ranging from 2-8 accompanying species. These mixed species foraging flocks are most comprised of Cory's Shearwaters (*Calonectris diomedea*), Audubon's Shearwaters (*Puffinus iherminieri*), Greater Shearwaters (*P. gravis*), and Pomarine Jaegers (*Stercorarius pomarinus*) during summer, and Black-legged Kittiwakes (*Rissa tridactyla*) and Herring Gulls (*Larus argentatus*) during the winter. Black-capped Petrels are not usually known to be attracted to feeding activities or assemblages of marine mammals; however, they have shown to be attracted to chum, and may be attracted to other waste discarded from ships and fishing vessels. This may mostly occur during times of low or unpredictable natural food abundance.

Movement / Home Range

As a pelagic seabird, the Black-capped Petrel spends most of its life over open seas. Use of marine habitats is largely confined to tropical and subtropical waters from 10° - 45°N latitude and roughly 65° - 80° W in the Atlantic. The species has an extent of occurrence (EOO) of 9,060,000 square kilometers (km²) (3,498,085.6 square miles [mi²]), meaning that this area consists of the shortest continuous boundary encompassing all known, inferred, or projected sites of species occurrence, excluding vagrancy.

Reproductive Strategy

Nest burrows are typically lined with material such as pine needles and small twigs brought into the burrow by the nesting pair. Although females usually spend lengthy periods of time away from the nest site before egg-laying, likely to forage and acquire sufficient nutritional reserves for egg production, males frequently enter nests during this time in anticipation of the female's return. Once eggs are laid, both sexes exhibit parental care through incubation and feeding of nestlings. It is suspected that active nest burrows may remain in use by the same pair year after year, although burrows are sometimes abandoned after death of one member of the pair. Fecundity is low, with only a single egg laid by the Black-capped Petrel. Breeding is believed to begin at five to eight years of age, with established pairs persisting for 10-20 years. The incubation period is 50-53 days, with chicks undergoing a lengthy nestling period of 80-85 days. Following their initial exit from the nest burrow, fledglings spend an additional 4-15 days both inside the burrow and just outside the burrow entrance, engaging in nightly bouts of wing and flight musculature exercise, before finally taking flight and abandoning the nest site. Thereafter, nest sites remain vacant until approximately mid-October, when the next nesting cycle begins.

» Other Resources

[NatureServe Explorer Species Reports](#)-- NatureServe Explorer is a source for authoritative conservation information on more than 50,000 plants, animals and ecological communities of the U.S and Canada. NatureServe Explorer provides in-depth information on rare and endangered species, but includes common plants and animals too. NatureServe Explorer is a product of NatureServe in collaboration with the Natural Heritage Network.

[ITIS Reports](#)-- ITIS (the Integrated Taxonomic Information System) is a source for authoritative taxonomic information on plants, animals, fungi, and microbes of North America and the world.

[FWS Digital Media Library](#) -- The U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's National Digital Library is a searchable collection of selected images, historical artifacts, audio clips, publications, and video." +